

Integrated approaches in a morphological analyzer of the Arabic language

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a system of a morphological analyzer of the Arabic language, by integrating several approaches and the viterbi algorithm. First approach is based on database for all the surface patterns in the Arabic language, second approach is Buckwalter Arabic morphological analyzer and the last approach is based on finite state automaton. With the integration of correspondence tables between affixes in these approaches. The combination between these approaches in our analyzer is very important. Our analyzer is tested on a morphological corpus of 200,000 words, which generalize the words of the Arabic language. The effectiveness of the proposed approaches is demonstrated experimentally and the results obtained are comparable to the state of the art. Moreover, it shows the interest and the advantages of integrating these approaches are to improve our morphological analyzer.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Morphological analysis is a very important step in various applications of natural language processing [1], [2]. Integration of approaches for morphological analyzer of the Arabic language is necessary [3], it requires the development of algorithms that can interpret and analyze word structure at many levels [4], such as processing linguistic rules, patterns of Arabic words and data dictionary, etc. Morphological analysis is used in a variety of applications of natural language processing [5], among them: information retrieval and extraction, machine translation, text mining, machine synthesis and Arabic learning systems [6].

The morphological analysis of Arabic is very complicated in the automatic processing because of the structure of complex word where we have stems, infixes, prefixes, suffixes, and complex patterns [7], [8]. It detects the different morphological entities in the word and provides a morphological representation. More, for each prefix or suffix can have its own syntactic attachment; this means that we have the resources to use the results of the morphological analysis stage in the higher stages of Arabic processing as syntactic analysis and error processing.

In recent years, several works have been developed in the axis of morphological analysis of the arabic language which are generally based on one of the following approaches: first approach based on linguistic rules [9]-[11], the second approach based on dictionary-based [10], [11], the following approach based on a word pattern [12]-[15], the fourth approach based on finite state automaton [16]-[18] and the last approach is hybrid approach which combines its different approaches [19].

In this work, we have proposed a study of approaches based on surface pattern and on finite state automaton. This allowed detecting the types of errors and the strengths and weaknesses of each analyzer. Subsequently, it will be very interesting to combine these approaches in a single analyzer to increase both the precision and the recall and to decrease the execution time compared to our first analyzers [20]. It is very important to combine several approaches to process and analyze words, in the arabic language, several analyzers have been developed, we can cite, for example, that of [10], [12], [18], [21]. In this article, we propose an integration of several approaches to build an Arabic morphological analyzer that meets all needs.

In sub-section 2.1, we will present a look on our morphological analyzer based on surface patterns. Sub-section 2.2, we will present an overview on our second morphological analyzer based on finite state automate and viterbi algorithm [22]. Section 3, we will present an integration of several approaches in order to build a morphological analyzer that deals with all cases of Arabic words. In section 5, we describe our morphological analyzer with tests and results. We provide our method for evaluating the approaches in the previous sections. In the last section, we conclude this work with some conclusions and recommendations.

2. METHOD

2.1. Morphological analysis based on the surface patterns

We have developed an approach to improve our morphological analysis which is based on the surface pattern of arabic language words. It is mainly based on the construction of the surface patterns database. This morphological analyzer determines one or many possible patterns for a given word, in order to find all possible analyzes of this word.

Patterns allow effectively modeling morphological variations within words and detecting the root of a word. in this axis, several works have been developed which use the pattern-root approach, among which we cite [12], [14]. All these works use for the morphological analysis of words the classical patterns of Arabic words. In our morphology analyzer, we use a new adapted pattern that we called surface patterns.

To build the database of surface patterns of Arabic words: For example the classical pattern of the word (جاندوا) is (فعلوا), but its surface pattern is (فالوا). The algorithm we used to build surface patterns from a word: For a word $w = l_1 l_2 \dots l_n$ (l_n Character of the word w) and R its root. The surface patterns of word w is $p = f_1 f_2 \dots f_n$ where:

$$\begin{cases} f_i \text{ is one of three letters "ف،ع،ل" if } l_i \in R \text{ and } l_i \notin \{ي،و،ا\} \\ f_i = l_i \text{ if } l_i \text{ is not in } R \text{ Where } l_i \in \{ي،و،ا\} \end{cases}$$

relying on the surface patterns database approach, for the word "قائلون" the root is "قال" and the surface pattern is "فائلون". The surface patterns of the root $R = g_1 g_2 \dots g_k$ (g_i is a character root) is $P' = f'_1 f'_2 \dots f'_k$ with:

$$\begin{cases} f'_i = \text{one of three letters (ف،ع،ل)} \text{ if } g_i \text{ is a non variant letter in } R \\ f'_i = g_i \text{ if not} \end{cases}$$

non-variant letter in a root R is a letter that stays the same when generating words from that root.

To perform out the morphological analysis with a word w by the surface patterns approach, we go through the following steps:

$$f(m; w) = \sum_{i=1}^N 1_{[m_i, w_i]}$$

we keep just the surface patterns having $f \neq 0$.

- Extraction only of the surface patterns of the solution roots from the surface patterns of the word analyze.
- Construction of roots from surface patterns, roots associated with word w and verification whether these roots exist in the root database or not.
- To test and evaluate our approach, we have constructed all surface patterns of words derived from the Arabic language. This step was handled by a group of Arabic language linguists. They used a set of Arabic language references.

Example:

The phases of analysis of the word "نقول":

- Searching for the surface patterns corresponding to the word "نقول". We find these surface patterns: $P_1 = \text{"نقول"}; P_2 = \text{"فعل"}$.
 - a. "قال" from the root "نقول".
 - b. "نقل" from the root "فعل".
- Extraction the surface patterns of the roots of P_1 and P_2 , we find both surface patterns of the roots $SR_1 = \text{"قال"}$ and $SR_2 = \text{"فعل"}$.
- Construction of the roots SR_1, SR_2 , from P_1, P_2 , and word W . We find the following root solutions: $R_1 = \text{"قال"}$ and $R_2 = \text{"نقل"}$.

For our surface patterns based analyzer (Figure 1). We used the following sources:

- Lexicon of 6,216 surface patterns. This lexicon contains all the morphological classes of words derived from the arabic language.
- Root dictionary containing 1,200 roots.
- Radical dictionary containing 6,000 radicals.

Figure 1. The steps of our morphological analyzer of Arabic words who use surface patterns

2.2. Morphological analyzer based on finite state automaton

The finite state automaton is an adaptive automaton which successively changes its structure according to the application of adaptive actions associated with the transition rules carried out by the automaton. The finite state automaton has great potential for to be used in natural language processing [16]. It able to simplify and represents complex linguistic situations such as ambiguities and non-determinisms especially in the Arabic language. Additionally, the recognition formalism can be put in place for a recognition formalism can be implemented for pre-processing texts for a variety of scenarios such as morphological analysis, syntactic verification, text interpretation, automatic translation and computer-assisted language learning [7], [23]. The form of the finite state automaton or adaptive automaton makes it possible to process the different classes of languages.

The finite state automaton analyzer [17] is an analyzer where each word of the Arabic language is represented by a path in this finite state automaton. To analyze a word, the finite-state automaton analyzer goes through the following two steps; The finite state automaton analyzer [24] is a morphological word analyzer, where every word of the Arabic language is represented by paths of the Arabic alphabets in this finite state automaton. For morphological analysis of a word, the finite-state automaton analyzer goes through the following two steps:

- Construction of a network of all the words of the Arabic language.
 - Search the possible solutions for our analyzer in this global network.
- This system based on very restricted dictionaries and searches the solutions in the global network using the Viterbi algorithm, and each word is modeled by a path, whose radical letters are presented by a state which loops on itself, and the affixes are presented by the characters forming the affixes.
- Example: For the words 'فجامعها', 'فداخلها'..., are presented by the following diagram (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Finite state automaton of words 'فداخلها', 'فجامعها'

Based on all the affixes of the Arabic language, we build the global network.

Our network is defined entirely by (Figure 3):

- The set of all the states is Q, it consists of all the characters composing the affixes (suffixe, prefixe and infixe), of state A, the start state q_i and the final state q_f:

$$Q = \{q_i, q_f, A, \text{"ف"}, \text{"و"}, \text{"ي"}, \text{"ل"}, \dots, \text{"ه"}, \text{"م"}, \text{"ت"}, \dots\}$$
- The set of possible transitions linking the characters of the affixes to the states A, q_i and q_f.

Figure 3. Diagram of our global network and possible transitions between states

How to find possible paths for the analysis of a word:

- To analyze a word W, we search the network for the different possible paths associated with W. These paths are given by:

$$S = \{ \xi \in B / P_r(w / \xi) \neq 0 \}$$

B: the possible paths in our network that have the same lengths as w.

- The solutions are the paths which make it possible to emit the word with a non-zero probability. we have adapted the Viterbi algorithm to the following format, to facilitate and reduce the calculation in (1):

$$\delta_t(c_j) = \max_{c_i \rightarrow c_j}^{NL} (\delta_{t-1}(c_i) a_{ij} 1_{c_j}(w_t)) \tag{1}$$

NL(x) is the non-zero value of x. We search for the states c_i which give nonzero values of:

$$\delta_{t-1}(c_i) \cdot a_{ij} \cdot 1_{c_j}(w_t)$$

$\delta_T(q_F)$ is the maximum probability of transmission of the word from a given path. By a recursive calculation we recover all the possible paths which give non-zero values (T the length of the word). With:

- a_{ij} : The state transition probability C_i to C_j , where:

$$a_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the transition is possible} \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

- w_t : T^{th} the character of the word w.

$$1_{c_j}(w_t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{si } c_j=w_t \\ 0 & \text{sinon} \end{cases} \quad \text{We take } 1_A(w_t)=1$$

Initialisation

$$\delta_0(c_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{si } c_i= q_I \\ 0 & \text{if not} \end{cases}$$

The test was carried out on 20,000 words representing different grammatical categories (verbs and nouns). 96% of these words were correctly analyzed and our finite state automaton analyzer proposed different possible analyzes for these words, while it did not do so for the remaining 4%. 95% of these errors were due to not taking into account the calculation links between prefixes, roots and suffixes in our analyzer (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Steps of our morphological analyzer based on finite state automata

To evaluate our approach based on finite state automata, we created the different dictionaries of suffixes, prefixes and radicals. After, we integrate the correspondence tables between affixes of the Arabic language. Then, from the list of prefixes, suffixes and infixes, we generate a global network of states as indicated previously, without using lexical dictionaries. This is the main advantage of our analyzer over Buckwalter arabic morphological analyzer and the analyzer based on finite state automata.

2.3. Integration of approaches to improve our analyzer

Our contribution is to develop a morphological analyzer of the Arabic language by integrating and combining approaches to improve our morphological analyzer. In this work, we have combined several approaches to improve a morphological analyzer that minimizes the error rate. For this, we have combined an approach that relies on the surface pattern with an approach that uses finite state automaton to analyze a given word.

We have many advantages in integrating and combining these approaches to develop and improve our analyzer. Among these advantages, we have reduction the size of the dictionaries used, unlike other analyzers. There is also the approach of the analyzer based on the surface patterns which uses the base of the surface patterns and models all the morphological variations of the derived words [20], [25]. On the other hand, the analyzer approach based on finite state automaton only articulates at the base of the roots. This approach, we generated a network of states without using lexical dictionaries. This is the main advantage of our analyzer over Buckwalter analyzer and surface pattern based analyzer.

In a finite state automaton based approach, the morphological analysis processes all the words, unlike the approach by patterns, which only gives the analyzes associated with the surface patterns existing in the database of patterns. The finite state automaton approach does not require the basics of linguistic knowledge to perform the morphological analysis of a word. However, these approaches have a few drawbacks. The surface pattern approach deals only with derived words, while the finite state automata approach process even non-derived words.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed adaptation comes from our study to a number of perspectives resulting from the words analyzed by our morphological analyzers of Arabic words. In this work, we have improved our morphological analyzer by integrating several approaches. These analyzers are essentially based on three concepts:

- The surface pattern [25];
- Buckwalter Arabic morphological analyzer [10] used with correspondence tables between Arabic language affixes;
- A finite state automaton [24].

A corpus of words from the Arabic language, which is developed by a group of linguists, is chosen as a grammatical support because it uses the same notation of the Arabic language, which is considered standard for natural language processing [17], [18].

The morphological analyzer has been implemented according to the structure of a network of finite state automaton. The database of surface patterns is made up of correspondence tables between affixes. A Viterbi algorithm was used to implement our network.

- The train dataset was 95% because it cover all categories, and test dataset was 5% of corpus which contains only the missed categories. As result, the morphological analyzer showed an accuracy of 95.09%.
- The morphological analyzer was trained on 95% of the morphological corpus and tested on the remaining 5%. The test dataset is only 5% but it contains a significant volume of words which have never been used for training.

As result, the morphological analyzer showed an accuracy of 95.09%. The results obtained by our analyzer are comparable to those of analyzers in general, but lower than those of specialized Arab analyzers which reach an accuracy of 97.09% (Table 1). Nevertheless, there are several possibilities for improvement, because it is possible to increase the size of the test morphological corpus and include more contextual information to disambiguate.

Table 1. Accuracy of each morphological analyzer

Morphological analyzers	Our surface-pattern based analyzer	Our finite state automaton-based analyzer	Buckwalter Arabic morphological analyzer	Our adaptive approaches
Accuracy	94,41%	95,09%	93,87%	97,09%

4. CONCLUSION

This article presents a concept of finite state automaton and the integration of tables of correspondence between affixes in the analysis approach. Moreover, it shows the importance of using surface patterns, detailing its working mechanism and the main areas of application and the great importance of its use in the field of natural language processing. The effectiveness of our proposed approach has been demonstrated experimentally. Our morphology analyzer obtained results comparable to general analyzers, with indicators and lower than those presented by specialized Arabic language analyzers. Improvements will be acceptable, as increasing the size of the morphological corpus for disambiguation. Finally, we hope to improve the architecture of adaptive approaches to morphological analyzes of Arabic words, by incorporating mechanisms pour choisir les types modèles de calcul avec des critères d'évaluation bien réelle et des règles de transition claires.

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